

Fixed Points in Continuous Non Decreasing Functions

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this paper is to establish a common fixed point theorem is established in G-complete fuzzy metric spaces in the sense of George and Veeramani besides discussing some related problems.

Keywords— *Continuous t-norm, Fuzzy metric space, G- Cauchy sequence, Housdroff and first countable*

INTRODUCTION

Gregori and Sapena [1] introduced the notion of fuzzy contractive mapping and proved fixed point theorems in varied classes of complete fuzzy metric spaces in the senses of George and Veeramani [2], Kramosil and Michalek [3] and Grabiec's [4]. Soon after, Mihet [5] proposed a fuzzy fixed point theorem for (weak) Banach contraction in M-complete fuzzy metric spaces. In this continuation, Mihet [6,7] further enriched the fixed point theory for various contraction

mappings in fuzzy metric spaces besides introducing variants of some new contraction mappings such as: Edelstein fuzzy contractive mappings, fuzzy ψ -contraction of (ϵ, λ) type etc. In the same spirit, Qiu et al. [8,9] also obtained some common fixed point theorems for fuzzy mappings under suitable conditions. In 2010 Pacurar and Rus in [10] , introduced the concept of cyclic ϕ -contraction and utilize the same to prove a fixed point theorem for cyclic ϕ -contraction in the natural setting of complete metric spaces besides investigating several related problems in respect of fixed points.

In this paper the notion of cyclic weak ϕ -contraction is introduced in a fuzzy metric space. Furthermore, fixed point theorem is established in G-complete fuzzy metric spaces in the sense of George and Veeramani besides discussing some related problems.

I. PRELIMINARIES

Definition – 1.1 A binary operation $\star: [0,1] \times [0,1] \rightarrow [0,1]$ is continuous t – norm if \star is satisfying the following conditions:

- 1.1 (i) \star is commutative and associative.
- 1.1 (ii) \star is continuous.
- 1.1 (iii) $a \star 1 = a$ for all $a \in [0,1]$.
- 1.1 (iv) $a \star b \leq c \star d$ whenever $a \leq c$ and $b \leq d$,
For $a, b, c, d \in [0,1]$.

Definition – 1.2 A triplet (X, M, \star) is said to be a fuzzy metric space if X is an arbitrary set, \star is a continuous t – norm and M is a fuzzy set on $X^2 \times (0, \infty)$ satisfying the following condition for all $x, y, z, s, t > 0$,

- 1.2 (FM – 1) $M(x, y, t) > 0$
- 1.2 (FM – 2) $M(x, y, t) = 1$ if and only if $x = y$.
- 1.2 (FM – 3) $M(x, y, t) = M(y, x, t)$

$$1.2 \text{ (FM - 4) } M(x, y, t) * M(y, z, s) \leq M(x, z, t + s)$$

$$1.2 \text{ (FM - 5) } M(x, y, \bullet) : (0, \infty) \rightarrow (0, 1] \text{ is continuous.}$$

Then M is called a fuzzy metric on X . The function $M(x, y, t)$ denote the degree of nearness between x and y with respect to t .

Example 1.3 Let (X, d) be a metric space. Define $a * b = \min\{a, b\}$ and

$$M(x, y, t) = \frac{t}{t + d(x, y)}$$

For all $x, y \in X$ and all $t > 0$. Then $(X, M, *)$ is a Fuzzy metric space.

It is called the Fuzzy metric space induced by d .

We note that, $M(x, y, t)$ can be realized as the measure of nearness between x and y with respect to t . It is known that $M(x, y, \cdot)$ is non decreasing for all $x, y \in X$. Let $(X, M, *)$ be a fuzzy metric space for $t > 0$, the open ball

$$B(x, r, t) = \{y \in X: M(x, y, t) > 1 - r\}.$$

Now, the collection $\{B(x, r, t): x \in X, 0 < r < 1, t > 0\}$ is a neighborhood system for a topology τ on X induced by the fuzzy metric M . This topology is Hausdorff and first countable.

Definition 1.5 A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in a fuzzy metric space $(X, M, *)$ is said to be a converges to x iff for each $\varepsilon > 0$ and each $t > 0$, $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $M(x_n, x, t) > 1 - \varepsilon$ for all $n \geq n_0$.

Definition 1.6 A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in a fuzzy metric space $(X, M, *)$ is said to be a G - Cauchy sequence converges to x iff for each $\varepsilon > 0$ and each $t > 0$, $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $M(x_m, x_n, t) > 1 - \varepsilon$ for all $m, n \geq n_0$.

II. MAIN RESULTS

Theorem – 2.1 Let $(X, M, *)$ be a fuzzy metric spaces, A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m be closed subsets of X and $Y = \bigcup_{i=1}^m A_i$ be G – complete. Suppose that $\phi: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a continuous non decreasing function with $\phi(r) > 0$ for each $r \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\phi(0) = 0$. If $f: Y \rightarrow Y$ satisfying,

$$\left(\frac{1}{M^2(fx, fy, t)} - 1\right) \leq \left(\frac{1}{M^2(x, fx, t) * M^2(y, fy, t)} - 1\right) - \phi\left(\frac{1}{M^2(x, fx, t) * M^2(y, fy, t)} - 1\right) \quad 2.1(i)$$

then f has a unique fixed point $z \in \bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i$.

Proof : Let $x_0 \in Y = \bigcup_{i=1}^m A_i$ and set $x_n = fx_{n-1}$ ($n \geq 1$). Clearly, we get $M(x_n, x_{n+1}, t) = M(fx_{n-1}, fx_n, t)$ for any $t > 0$. Beside for any $n \geq 0$, there exists $i_n \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ such that $x_n \in A_{i_n}$ and $x_{n+1} \in A_{i_{n+1}}$. Then by 4.2.4(i), (for $t > 0$) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1}{M^2(x_n, x_{n+1}, t)} - 1\right) &= \left(\frac{1}{M^2(fx_{n-1}, fx_n, t)} - 1\right) & 2.1(ii) \\ &\leq \left(\frac{1}{M^2(x_{n-1}, fx_{n-1}, t) * M^2(x_n, fx_n, t)} - 1\right) \\ &\quad - \phi\left(\frac{1}{M^2(x_{n-1}, fx_{n-1}, t) * M^2(x_n, fx_n, t)} - 1\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \left(\frac{1}{M^2(x_{n-1}, x_n, t) * M^2(x_n, x_{n+1}, t)} - 1 \right)$$

Which implies that

$$M^2(x_n, x_{n+1}, t) \geq M^2(x_{n-1}, x_n, t) * M^2(x_n, x_{n+1}, t)$$

and hence

$$M(x_n, x_{n+1}, t) \geq M(x_{n-1}, x_n, t) * M(x_n, x_{n+1}, t)$$

For all $n \geq 1$ and so $\{M(x_{n-1}, x_n, t)\}$ is non decreasing sequence of positive real numbers in $(0,1]$.

Let $S(t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} M^2(x_{n-1}, x_n, t)$. Now we show that $S(t) = 1$ for all $t > 0$. If not, there exists some $t > 0$ such that $S(t) < 1$. Then, on making $n \rightarrow +\infty$ in 4.2.4(ii), we obtain

$$\left(\frac{1}{S(t)} - 1 \right) \leq \left(\frac{1}{S(t)} - 1 \right) - \phi \left(\frac{1}{S(t)} - 1 \right)$$

Which is a contradiction. Therefore $M^2(x_n, x_{n+1}, t) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow +\infty$. Now for each positive integer p we have

$$M(x_n, x_{n+p}, t) \geq M\left(x_n, x_{n+1}, \frac{t}{p}\right) * M\left(x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}, \frac{t}{p}\right) * \dots * M\left(x_{n+p-1}, x_{n+p}, \frac{t}{p}\right)$$

It follows that $\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} M(x_{n-1}, x_n, t) \geq 1 * 1 * \dots * 1 = 1$

So that $\{x_n\}$ is a G-Cauchy sequence. As Y is G-complete, then there exists $y \in Y$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} x_n = y$. It follows that the iterative sequence $\{x_n\}$ has a infinite numbers of terms in A_i for each $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Since Y is G-complete, for each $A_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ one can exists a subsequence of $\{x_n\}$ that converges to y . By virtue of the fact that each $A_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, m$ is closed, we conclude that $y \in \bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i \neq \emptyset$. Obviously, $\bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i$ is closed and G-complete. Now we consider the restriction of f on $\bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i$, i.e. $f|_{\bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i} : \bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i \rightarrow \bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i$ thus $f|_{\bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i}$ has a unique fixed point in $\bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i$, say z , which is obtained by iteration form the starting point $x_0 \in Y$. To this end, we have show that $x_n \rightarrow z$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then, by 4.2.1(i), we have

$$\left(\frac{1}{M^2(x_n, z, t)} - 1 \right) \leq \left(\frac{1}{M^2(x_{n-1}, x_{n-2}, t)} - 1 \right) - \phi \left(\frac{1}{M^2(x_{n-1}, x_{n-2}, t)} - 1 \right)$$

Now letting $n \rightarrow +\infty$, we get

$$\left(\frac{1}{M^2(y, z, t)} - 1 \right) \leq \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y, y, t)} - 1 \right) - \phi \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y, y, t)} - 1 \right)$$

Which is contradiction if $M(y, z, t) < 1$, and so, we conclude that $z = y$. Obviously z is the unique fixed point of f .

Theorem - 2.2 Let (X, M, \star) be a fuzzy metric spaces, A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m be closed subsets of X and $Y = \bigcup_{i=1}^m A_i$ be G-complete. Suppose that $\phi: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a continuous non decreasing function with $\phi(r) > 0$ for each $r \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\phi(0) = 0$. If $f: Y \rightarrow Y$ satisfying,

$$\left(\frac{1}{M^2(fx, fy, t)} - 1\right) \leq \left(\frac{1}{M^2(x, fx, t) * M^2(y, fy, t)} - 1\right) - \phi \left(\frac{1}{M^2(x, fx, t) * M^2(y, fy, t)} - 1\right) \quad 2.2(i)$$

and there exists a sequence $\{y_n\}$ in Y such that $M(y_n, fy_n, t) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow +\infty$ for any $t > 0$, then $y_n \rightarrow z$ as $n \rightarrow +\infty$, provides that the fuzzy metric M is triangular, and z is the unique fixed point of f in $\bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i$.

Proof: By Theorem – 4.2.4 we have that $z \in \bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i$ is the unique fixed point of f . Now, from the triangular inequality of M and 4.2.2(i), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_n, z, t)} - 1\right) &\leq \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_n, fy_n, t)} - 1\right) + \left(\frac{1}{M^2(fy_n, fz, t)} - 1\right) \\ \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_n, z, t)} - 1\right) &\leq \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_n, fy_n, t)} - 1\right) \\ &\quad + \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_n, fy_n, t) * M^2(fz, z, t)} - 1\right) \\ &\quad - \phi \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_n, fy_n, t) * M^2(fz, z, t)} - 1\right) \end{aligned}$$

Which is equivalent to

$$\left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_n, z, t)} - 1\right) \leq \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_n, fy_n, t)} - 1\right)$$

From the last inequality we conclude that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \phi \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_n, z, t)} - 1\right) = 0$$

Since
$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_n, fy_n, t)} - 1\right) = 0.$$

then, by the property of ϕ , we conclude that $M(y_n, z, t) \rightarrow 1$, which is equivalent to say that $y_n \rightarrow z$ as $n \rightarrow +\infty$.

Theorem – 2.3 Let (X, M, \star) be a fuzzy metric spaces, A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m be closed subsets of X and $Y = \bigcup_{i=1}^m A_i$ be G – complete. Suppose that $\phi: [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is a continuous non decreasing function with $\phi(r) > 0$ for each $r \in (0, +\infty)$ and $\phi(0) = 0$. If $f: Y \rightarrow Y$ satisfying,

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1}{M^2(fx, fy, t)} - 1\right) &\leq \left(\frac{1}{M^2(x, fx, t) * M^2(y, fy, t)} - 1\right) \\ &\quad - \phi \left(\frac{1}{M^2(x, fx, t) * M^2(y, fy, t)} - 1\right) \quad 2.3(i) \end{aligned}$$

and there exists a sequence $\{y_n\}$ in Y such that $M(y_{n+1}, fy_n, t) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow +\infty$ for any $t > 0$, then there exists $x \in Y$ such that $M(y_n, f^n x, t) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow +\infty$ provides that the fuzzy metric M is triangular.

Proof : Once again, according to the proof of Theorem – 4.2.4, we observe that for any initial point $x \in Y, z \in \bigcap_{i=1}^m A_i$ is the unique fixed point of f . Moreover, for any $t > 0$, $0 < M(y_n, z, t) < 1$ and $0 < M(y_{n+1}, z, t) < 1$. Set y as a limit of a convergent sequence $\{y_n\}$ in Y . Now, from the triangularity of M and 4.2.6(i), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_{n+1}, z, t)} - 1\right) &\leq \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_{n+1}, f y_n, t)} - 1\right) + \left(\frac{1}{M^2(f y_n, f z, t)} - 1\right) \\ \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_n, z, t)} - 1\right) &\leq \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_n, f y_n, t)} - 1\right) \\ &+ \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_n, f y_n, t) * M^2(z, f z, t)} - 1\right) \\ &- \phi \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y_n, f y_n, t) * M^2(z, f z, t)} - 1\right) \end{aligned}$$

Then, on making $n \rightarrow +\infty$ in the above inequality, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y, z, t)} - 1\right) &\leq \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y, f y, t) * M^2(z, f z, t)} - 1\right) \\ &- \phi \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y, f y, t) * M^2(z, f z, t)} - 1\right) \quad 2.3(ii) \end{aligned}$$

Clearly 4.2.6(ii) is true if and only if $\phi \left(\frac{1}{M^2(y, z, t)} - 1\right) = 0$. By the property of the function ϕ , must be $\left(\frac{1}{M^2(y, z, t)} - 1\right) = 0$ and thus $y = z$. Consequently, we have $M(y_n, f^n x, t) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow +\infty$.

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